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“Exploring Perspectives on Death and Dying Among Final-Year Undergraduate Medical Students at Tbilisi Medical Academy, Georgia”

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Type: Oral Presentation

“Explore of Real and Virtual patients as professional perception and motivation for preclinical medical students”

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“Introducing GOTs (growth-oriented tests) – relative freedom with responsibility”

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Exploring Perspectives on Death and Dying Among Final-Year Undergraduate Medical Students at Tbilisi Medical Academy, Georgia

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Background

Death is a universal phenomenon that has fascinated mankind for centuries. Despite this fascination, a prevailing cultural perspective often frames death as a medical failure. Limited attention has been given to understanding how medical students respond to death and dying, and whether the current undergraduate curriculum provides sufficient opportunities to develop competences in scientific, ethical, and legal domains.

Summary of Work

The objective of this study was to investigate the perspectives on death held by final semester undergraduate students enrolled in the 6th-year Medicine program at Tbilisi Medical Academy, Georgia, and to evaluate the extent to which the program has equipped them to address matters related to death and dying from their perspective. We employed mixed methods research. Attitudes toward death were measured using a validated Death Attitude Profile-Revised (DAP-R) questionnaire and another questionnaire to measure perceived preparedness and teaching about death. The qualitative component involved face-to-face interviews conducted in the form of focus group meetings.

Summary of Results

23 students completed the questionnaire. 90.9% of the students reported that they had not experienced the death of a patient during the program. 54.5% of the students declared that they feel unprepared to deal with terminal patients.

Regarding the depth and adequacy of the program's approach to death-related themes, 54.5% of students found it to be superficial and insufficient, while 31.8% considered it to be superficial but sufficient. In the context of DAP-R, the highest mean was observed for death avoidance, followed by escape acceptance, neutral acceptance, fear of death, and approach acceptance.

Discussion and Conclusions

This study reveals significant gaps in the exposure and preparedness of final semester medical students regarding death and dying. Based on the findings, future directions should include curriculum enhancements to better prepare students for the complexities of end-of-life care. Strategies to increase exposure should be considered, and ongoing evaluation of the curriculum's effectiveness in addressing these issues is crucial.

Take Home Messages

* A majority of final semester medical students lack firsthand experience with patient death, highlighting the need for increased exposure during medical education. * Perceived lack of teaching about death-related themes highlights the importance of curriculum enhancements to better prepare students for addressing end-of-life care complexities.

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EXPOSURE TO REAL AND VIRTUAL PATIENTS AS PROFESSIONAL PERCEPTION AND MOTIVATION FOR PRECLINICAL MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Background

Over the past two years, Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy restructured a part of its preclinical curriculum by introducing a new learning path called Clinical Reasoning (CR). Implemented in the initial 6 semesters, CR dedicated 5 weeks per semester to real patient cases. In addition to the standard basic sciences curriculum, CR introduced the “Integration Week” model, allowing preclinical students to interact with real patients and solve “CyberPatient” virtual cases. This approach aims to enhance critical thinking, independent judgment, and application of theoretical knowledge in clinical settings. We aimed to assess the impact of exposing preclinical students to real and virtual patients on their professional perception and motivation.

Summary of Work

As the questionnaire was optional, 60 of 69 third-semester students completed the quantitative survey. The 8-item online questionnaire was distributed using the Google Forms platform. A total of 60 responses were collected to explore possible correlations and insights regarding students’ experiences with both real and virtual patient encounters, evaluating the potential impact on their professional perception and motivation to continue their medical studies.

Summary of Results

Out of 60 participants, 74.6% confirmed their overall motivation to study medicine increased after participating in the CyberPatient and real patient activities. 74.6% agreed meeting with a real patient increased their understanding of the challenges and responsibilities of being a medical professional, while 79.7% declared that real patient interaction helped them understand the importance of empathy and patient-centered care in medical practice. 67.8% said they would recommend other students to attend virtual patient case discussions and 67.8% stated they would like to participate in virtual patient discussions again.

Discussion and Conclusions

Exposure to real patient and virtual patient interactions could bring unique learning experiences to preclinical medical students. By allowing students to make independent decisions via virtual cases, Integration Week can cultivate critical thinking skills and enhance clinical decision-making, while focusing on empathy and the understanding of the real-life challenges of a medical practitioner.

Take Home Messages

Innovative medical education learning experiences can yield unexpected benefits, shaping the professional skills, perception, and motivation of future medical and healthcare professionals.

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Introducing GOTs (growth-oriented tests) – relative freedom with responsibility

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Background

Adaptation to a university environment is not easy for first-year medical students. The hardest part is learning how to prepare for exams. Because of this, at Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy (TMA), we decided to introduce an assessment system that would not only evaluate the gained knowledge but also reduce stress, make students feel more confident about their knowledge, and lead to better results on final exams. So, we gradually implemented growth-oriented tests (GOTs). In the process of and after implementation, we conducted several studies to compare the standard-graded quizzes with the new ones, the GOTs.

Summary of Work

We studied the academic performance of students who took GOTs and compared them with those who took the standard quizzes. Concomitantly, we conducted multiple focus groups with students and surveys of lecturers to describe their experiences.

Summary of Results

Academic performance We have analyzed the data from the exams held before and after the introduction of GOTs. The comparison showed prominent differences, especially in the first semester. The final exam results showed a pass rate increase

from 64.5% to 90.9% and 43.4% to 70.2% in different groups of students. Also, average scores were significantly improved—by 13% and by 11.9% for the different groups. Students In focus groups, the vast majority of students (100 students in total) evaluated GOTs as the most friendly, low-stress, student-oriented tests that had the greatest impact on their knowledge, adaptation, and preparation for final exams. Lecturers In total, 17 lecturers participated in the online survey. Responses reveal that all 17 lecturers (100%) like the new system. 16 lecturers (93.1%) strongly or partially agree that students are more mobilized, and about 11 lecturers (65%) are sure they would like to have GOTs as they were students.

Discussion and Conclusions

To conclude, the academic performance and students' and lecturers' opinions all indicate that GOTs are more efficient, less stressful, and more student-oriented than the graded quizzes.

Take Home Messages

Switching from regular, graded quizzes to formative, feedback-oriented assessments improves the performance of students on final exams and reduces stress during preparation, which helps them achieve their goals much more efficiently.